

Teachers' beliefs and challenges of using multimedia for teaching visuals in social work: A study of Bangladeshi government college

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ABSTRACT

Social Work (SW) educators are increasingly using a number of visual aids in their lessons to make the learning process more effective. To teach the dominant SW courses, educators in this discipline are likely to use relevant photographs, videos, posters, graphs and other visual contents in addition to textbooks. The goal of this study is to explore the current beliefs and challenges of educators by using multimedia for teaching visuals in SW courses at the tertiary level. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the fact that this study took place at a government institution, only educators were chosen based on their availability, experience, and willingness to take part in this research. The data was gathered through qualitative methodology. A semi-structured interview schedule was used to collect information, and finally, using the thematic approach, the data was analyzed. The findings show that incorporating visual aids with multimedia in the classroom provides a number of benefits. It enhances student comprehension, boosts participation, and keeps students' attention focused on the substance of the lesson. The research findings also reveal that educators encounter certain obstacles, such as inadequate proficiency in utilizing multimedia with visual aids, insufficient availability of multimedia classrooms and equipment, a lack of proper training and low internet speed, the absence of backup power sources, and a lack of additional financial incentives for their supplementary efforts. The results of this study indicate that the integration of visual multimedia can augment the attractiveness and comprehensibility of instructional sessions. The participation of students in a multimedia-based classroom environment has the potential to function as a catalyst for their academic motivation.

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study:

Modern technology-based teaching methods have made traditional learning approaches less effective. Educators make every effort to leverage the most recent technological advancements in the area of education in order to overcome many of the challenges of traditional practices (Aloraini, 2012). The goal of technology is to develop innovative methods of teaching and learning that are based on contemporary thinking (Neo & Neo, 2004). Accordingly, using multimedia for teaching different subjects through visuals in the education sector is a significant component of the overall use of educational technology. Educators and students seem to agree on the need to incorporate technology into the classroom and learning environment. The SW educator is always being asked to come up with and use strategies and approaches that help bridge the gap between the classroom and the field of work in educational settings (Moss, 2000). Historically, SW educators have relied on textbook case studies, multimedia tools, guest lecturers, and the instructors' own practice experiences to demonstrate theories, concepts, and issues in the classroom. Students learn better, when their teachers use visual aids to help them remember complicated ideas and information (Moss, 2000). Teachers value visuals because they help pupils create connections between knowledge, memorize portions of content rapidly, and recall information.

For many years, the department of Social Work at Bhola Government College (BGC) has relied on the traditional lecture technique to teach its students their subjects. It is very rare for the researcher to be able to use multimedia with different visual tools to teach his classes. At the researcher's college, visual multimedia could have a big impact on the way SW courses are taught and learned. It has the potential to develop innovative approaches to improving the quality of teaching, learning, and academic facilities. In addition, it will help the researcher's college Social Work students improve their skills as well. Therefore, this study focuses on teacher's beliefs and challenges of using multimedia for teaching with visuals in SW courses at a Government College, Bhola, Bangladesh.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Many educational institutions in our country follow a more traditional teaching style (Islam, 2020). Conventional methods do not encourage students to be actively involved in their education. Instead, they focus on the teacher's role (Sultana and Shahabul, 2018). Teachers give their lectures to their students, making them the main source of knowledge. Students are rarely given the opportunity to put their own ideas into action. They just retain what their instructor has stated (Ahmed, 2018). Students are not encouraged to take an active role in their education when taught according to the traditional teaching methods. Currently, only a small number of instructors at government institutions incorporate multimedia projectors, computers, laptops, digital devices, and smart phones into their classroom teaching. A variety of audio-visual effects may be created in learning settings using multimedia. Innovative SW educators have taken advantage of this opportunity to extend and enliven the course's content by using images, texts, audio, and videos, among other media (Ballantyne, 2008). Therefore, for fulfilling this kind of learning gaps, the researcher is interested in finding out what educators think about the use of multimedia for teaching through visuals in SW courses at Bangladesh's government colleges.

1.3 Rationale

Bangladesh's government is now promoting multimedia classrooms as one of the benchmarks for transforming the country into a "digital Bangladesh" across all levels of education. It has seen a huge development for multimedia that can be used in classrooms at government institutions in the last few years. Within a variety of institutions, particularly among government colleges, the current government has already constructed 1600 multimedia classrooms and is actively creating additional multimedia-based classrooms (Sultana & Haque, 2018). The effectiveness of multimedia in teaching and learning has been examined from a variety of perspectives. The new teaching method wants students to picture the lesson by not making images in their brains while hearing and making them in a text. According to Penuel et al. (2000), it is possible for

students to assemble, synthesize, and construct an eye-catching experience of visible materials that they perceive audibly while using multimedia-enabled instruction. Teachers can incorporate visual aids in the classroom to increase student attention, understanding, and retention of ideas and topics to make the learning process more fascinating, entertaining, and successful.

Using visual aids in the classroom is seen as a good way to keep students engaged and excited about learning (Cakir, 2006). Consequently, it seems that the employment of visual aids is beneficial to both instructors and students in the classroom. In this regard, research has not been undertaken to use visual resources for teaching SW at the college level in Bangladesh. However, this study will undermine the teacher's views and beliefs about using multimedia for teaching visuals in SW courses at government colleges in Bangladesh. It is anticipated that the outcomes of the study will assist SW instructors in understanding the usefulness of employing visual aids in the classroom and in discovering any prospective benefits of them. Aside from this, it is associated with Bangladeshi college education, which was a consideration in selecting this topic.

1.4 Objectives and research questions

The complete aim of the study is to know the teachers' beliefs and challenges of using multimedia for teaching visuals in SW courses at government colleges in Bangladesh. The following are the study's particular objectives: a) to find out the present beliefs and practices of teachers regarding multimedia for teaching visuals in SW courses at BGC; b) to identify how multimedia is useful for teaching visuals in SW courses at this college; and c) to identify the difficulties associated with the use of multimedia for teaching visuals in the dominant SW courses at this college. Specifically, the following three research questions are addressed throughout the study:

- a) What are the teachers' beliefs about the learning benefits of multimedia with visuals?
- b) Which SW courses benefit most from incorporating visual multimedia instructions?
- c) What challenges do SW teachers confront when utilising multimedia to teach visually?

1.5 Limitation of the study

There are a few gaps in the existing study that should be pointed out. Because of the continuing COVID-19 epidemic, it was decided that just one Government College would be used to collect research data. The researcher's main affiliation was with Bhola Government College; therefore, doing research at another institution was not an option under such conditions. This study was conducted in a very short amount of time. Also, there would not be enough money since it was self-funded research. Despite the obstacles, the researcher was able to go through the interviews with the support of college administration and the department's fellow colleagues.

Literature Review

2.1 Teacher's beliefs about the learning benefits of multimedia

A mixture of text, graphics, animations, audio, and video that we will watch and pay attention to each day is called multimedia (Vaughan, 2006). Multimedia has an important part in education, from basic to higher levels. Lessons are more comprehensible and comfortable when multimedia is used in learning and teaching (Ahmed, 2018). Multimedia creates newer technology driven proactive teaching approaches in the classroom as well as a new proactive method for the expansion of views and concepts for teaching and learning (Islam, 2020). Scholars have agreed that using multimedia in classrooms has unquestionable benefits. The International Conference on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering, Dai and Fan (2012) presented their paper on "Discussion about the Pros and Cons and Recommendations for Multimedia Teaching in Local Vocational Schools" mentioning various advantages to teaching through multimedia over traditional ways of teaching. They

mentioned their findings through the survey that teachers may also show their lectures in a more innovative and flexible way by using multimedia. It helps educators to learn innovative teaching methods that improve the standard of teaching. Educators may help pupils comprehend more by employing a variety of images and audio-visual materials.

Using multimedia projectors in classrooms at the tertiary level in Bangladesh is not a new concept (Amin, Azim & kalam, 2018). It assists instructors in capturing students' attention, engaging them in learning, explaining difficult topics, inspiring creativity, and having a bit of fun. Learners may more readily visualize complex topics or processes when static or dynamic multimedia is used. The use of a multimedia projector in an English language teaching (ELT) classroom aided instructors in bringing about a dramatic and dynamic shift in the classroom ambiance as well as instructional strategies (Amin, Azim & kalam, 2018). They showed that teachers can present a lesson not only orally but also visually using a multimedia projector in the classroom, which encourages pupils to pay greater attention in the classroom. Pun (2013) also looked at the benefits of adopting a multimedia projector in the classroom for English language instructors and learners. Learners are also allowed to express their individual thoughts in a more dynamic way in the multimedia classroom.

2.2 Using multimedia for teaching with visuals

It goes without saying that the visual organs of the human body are the most significant organs in the body (Wang and Wang, 1992). Only multimedia instruction has the ability to excite the students' many sensory organs when compared to other instructional approaches (Zhen, 2016). Visual lectures are more engaging than conventional lectures because they are more interactive. Photographs help to make the material more focused and concentrated, and they help people learn more than just by reading about it. Students' attention is drawn to key aspects by using educational videos, images, and animations. Students do better in class because of the interactive nature of visual lectures (Khan et al. 2020). Konyalioğlu, Aksu & Şenel (2012) conducted research on the preference of visualization in teaching and learning absolute value. The research focuses on instructors' preferences for using visualization in the problem-solving and how much they encourage their pupils to do so. This research discovered that visualization has a good influence on the introductory stages of teaching the absolute value notion.

Today, successful teaching and learning would be impossible without the use of various ICT and digital educational techniques and innovations (Andresen & van den Brink, 2002). As a result, ICT and multimedia-enabled instruction in many fields, including Social Work, is becoming increasingly crucial. Focuses on student assessments of computer applications used in introduction to social work methodologies courses; Seabury and Maple (1993) discovered that social work students were quite pleased with the multimedia teaching. The study's findings that users enhanced their learning, acquired a sense of competence in the student area, and got better confident with the use of technologies suggest that multimedia is an effective technique of imparting training in the information and skills required for SW practice.

2.3 Using visual tools for teaching SW Courses

There has been a lot of research on how technology can be used in SW education, but most of it has been about online education or distance learning. A few studies have looked at how technology can be used in the classroom to make students more active and more likely to interact with each other and with their teacher (Holmes et. al, 2015). Ballantyne & Knowles (2007) investigated the learning prospects of Scottish and Canadian SW students using a multimedia case-based learning object. The study found that the most of the students acceded that by using the multimedia case study substantially improved their learning. The students appreciated studying with the multimedia case material; they saw distinctions in learning from multimedia cases vs text-based instances; and multimedia case studies helped them comprehend the complexity of practice better than text-based courses. The multimedia example was thought to be more real, inspiring, lasting, and easy.

Hallet & Faria (2006) compared the use of "advanced multimedia" as an alternate to a discourse in order to express details to the learners of SW and the learners of speech and language therapy. They found that students retained more information and reported a preference for multimedia both immediately after the presentation and after three weeks later when they were given the option to choose between the two methods of instruction. A study by Hansen et al. (2002) examined the effectiveness of a multimedia interactive CD-ROM aimed at educating Social Workers and health professionals on hearing abilities. There was a significant increase in the recognition of instructional material by beginning students, as well as an increase in their own self-reported dependence on the application of hearing abilities, according to the findings. Student feedback on the program's usefulness has been overwhelmingly positive. Creative SW instructors have been using photos, audio, and videos in the curriculum to improve and liven up instruction since it became possible to do so uttered by Ballantyne & Knowles (2007). The use of multimedia teaching helps to create a more conducive learning environment in the classroom. Learners are more actively involved in the learning process when projectors are used in lectures.

The use of a visual-multimedia presentation may assist in boosting the engagement of students in a learning session. Visual presentations offer more full communicative content than the lecture method. Therefore, the use of multimedia with visual in the classroom encourages two-way communication between instructors and learners (Khan et al. 2020). Ozaslan and Maden (2013) conducted significant research in which they discovered that students learn more effectively when materials are given with the use of visuals. Students are more likely to pay attention when the contents are presented visually on PowerPoint slides. Some individuals believe that PPT presentations are not always beneficial for teaching purposes. Therefore, the students of this discipline have to acquire knowledge from various social science discipline. In this case, they need to enrich their learning with various non-major courses like Human behaviour and Psychology, Social Statistics, Demography, Computer Science, Public Health and so on. All of these non-major courses are easy for students to learn if they are taught through a variety of diagrams, graphs, maps and other materials through power point presentation with audio-visual effects.

2.4 Challenges of using multimedia with visuals for SW educators

To satisfy the need for high-quality education for everyone, Bangladesh's higher education organizations have expanded dramatically during the previous several decades (Sultana& Shahabul, 2018). Despite the fact that technology and education have become more integrated, a number of obstacles still stand in the way of broad adoption. Some of these challenges are systemic, while others have to do with the underlying technology. Teaching new technology or using multimedia in the classroom might be challenging because instructors lack the required training or ongoing professional development (Ahmed, 2018). Due to budget constraints and other financial issues, BGC is desiderating sufficient multimedia items such as computers, laptops, overhead projectors, and interactive white boards. Teachers, on the other hand, are under more pressure since they must commit more time and effort to producing better content than they have in the past. Their argument was that just a small number of educators use multimedia, but the majority of educators do not. In addition, they have noted that there is a lack of adequate training for instructors, a lack of multimedia classrooms, slower internet, and other impediments to regular multimedia use.

Research Methodology

3.1 Research design and the research context

A qualitative research design was used in this study, and it was done in just one format. The researcher or investigator believes that a qualitative approach is suitable while exploring a new field of study or planning to identify and theorize essential subjects (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Additionally, they stated that qualitative methodologies will be employed to obtain data from instructors and students, since they are significant elements of educational settings. This qualitative study was done to provide a real picture of whether multimedia-based Social Work education will be successful and relevant from the standpoint of teachers' perspective. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic scenario, instructors were chosen by convenience sampling based on their availability

and expertise of current technology, as well as their willingness to provide their precious time and cooperation for conducting this study at a government college in Bhola, Bangladesh.

3.2 Description of the Research Instruments

Interviews were the only research tool used in this study because this study was conducted in a very short amount of time. This tool is widely considered one of the most important and widely used tools in social research (Newcomer, Hatry & Wholey, 2015). Research objectivity dictates the questions that an interviewer asks during a conversation with a respondent in order to gather information about their life experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016). It is possible for respondents to express their perspectives on the study topic via semi-structured interviews. The interviewee, on the other hand, will freely express his thoughts and will not abide by the interviewer's strict instructions. A set of questions was produced for teachers to help them prepare for interviews. By using an open-ended questionnaire, researchers have the opportunity to delve into their subject matter in more depth.

3.3 Method of data collection and data analysis

A semi-structured interview was used to collect information from the Social Work Department at Bhola Government College. The respondents were all from this department. The language of the interview was Bangla. The researcher collected the data through the face to face and online interview and the duration of each interview lasted 10 to 15 minutes. The dialogue between the interviewer and the respondents was captured using audio recorders, which were placed in the restricted room. The researcher used the code for analyzing the data for conducting the interview from the five educators. Among five educators, three were male teachers and two were female teachers. T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5 are the codes for the five teachers. A narrative analysis of the data was performed afterwards. Based on research questions, the researcher briefly addressed all of the semi-structured interview questions in a short amount of time. Direct quotations were often employed during data processing to highlight the authenticity of the actual situation.

3.4 Ethical Consideration

An informed consent form was presented to all teachers who took part in this research project. All of them had signed that permission form. It included all of the ethical concerns that were relevant at the time. This research makes no mention of the participants' names at any point in the text. Their identities will not be divulged at this time either and the substance of this study is devoid of any sensory concerns.

Findings and Discussions

4.1 Findings from the teachers' interview

The data was collected through a semi-structured interview protocol consisting of thirteen distinct questions that were categorized into three sections. In section one (findings from 4.1.1 to 4.1.5, number questions), the questions asked about the opinions and ideas of the teacher's beliefs about using different multimedia tools. The researcher wanted to know how they felt about the use of different visual aids in their SW classes. Each of the five educators had a similar reaction to the question. They agreed that they use different visual aids from time to time, like photos, maps, and color posters, PPT slides but they think these visual aids should be used regularly so that the students can easily understand the SW concepts.

In the interview, T1 mentioned,

"Using multimedia in teaching is a very positive aspect, especially visual aids, which are important when it comes to integrating multimedia into SW classes. We can give the students a concrete idea with the help of pictures. SW educators can easily show different SW terms on the posters. It is possible that any learning

session can be more fruitful by using posters as well as maps. Overall, visual aids play a very vital role in the teaching of SW students."

The researcher also wanted to know their views on the learning benefits of using PowerPoint to teach SW classes. When it came to responding to the question, all five educators came up with the same answer. In the interview, T3 responded, "In my opinion, PowerPoint is the most popular visual tool for presenting any topic clearly. Here, you can show the necessary photographs, videos, or animations for understanding the lecture clearly. Students can grasp the content easily by seeing and hearing the lecture lively." Another query asked the educators what they thought about the videos being used to help students quickly understand the ideas in their classes. The majority of the teachers agreed that they think videos are the best visual tools to help the students understand the subject matter more clearly. When they play topic-related videos, students feel very comfortable. Their concentration on the lecture increases, and they try to find the meaning of the words with the video's main theme.

In the interview, T2 replied,

"The video certainly helps the students understand different things quickly. In this way, the attention of students can be easily drawn to that particular subject, and this will help the students better understand the specific topic. Moreover, if you take a class by showing a video, the hard work of the teacher will be lessened. "

The second section of the interview was about using multimedia to teach with visuals in the most dominant SW courses (findings from 4.1.6 to 4.1.10). They were asked about how often they use statistical tables, graphs, and diagrams to help students better understand SW courses and what the most effective and least effective visual tools were. From the interviews of the five educators, it is said that the most effective visual tools are PowerPoint as well as Photoshop, and the least effective tools are graphics and animation. In the interview, T1 mentioned, "In my opinion, PPT is the most effective visual tool because I can show the slides with texts, pictures, and videos with audio-visual effects at the same time. Photoshop and graphics are the less effective tools because utilizing these tools for SW classes is very arduous and you need to be very expert to use them."

One of the interviewees, T3, uttered,

"Statistics is a non-major SW course where different tables and diagrams are used frequently." "From my point of view, students can understand better if we present any statistical explanation or results with these elements through the presentation of visual tools."

In addition, the final section (findings from 4.1.11 to 4.1.13) asked for possible suggestions on how the educators might solve the problems they face. All the educators mentioned that they have suffered various challenges, such as insufficient electricity and an inadequate multimedia classroom. a lack of various materials, such as laptops, projectors, and internet access Finally, they mentioned some facilities that should be introduced in their department, such as more multimedia classrooms, more laptops, and other facilities.

One of the educators, T4, mentioned,

"Primarily, I need a laptop. Then I will need access to the internet, as well as financial assistance. The scarcity of laptop computers is a serious issue. The college or the government cannot provide all of this assistance."

Teachers have many problems to deal with when creating visual presentations or PPT slides for their classes. During the course of preparing visual presentations for their courses, the majority of them mentioned that they take into consideration several typical challenges. T1 mentioned, "Some teachers do not want to create

visual content because they do not have a personal laptop or internet facility at home. Moreover, creating visual material is a very laborious task, and they do not get any honorarium for this. It is time-consuming work, indeed.”

Based on the teachers' interview findings above, educators say that one of the best things about visual aids is that they help them put lessons into context. Using visual aids, teachers may improve their classes and provide context for their students. Learners may readily draw connections between the visual aids and the lectures. As a result, when pictures are used with lectures, they have a long-lasting effect on the minds of the learners who see them. Mathew and Alidmat (2013) discovered same findings in their research.

4.2 Discussions on the teachers' interview findings

4.2.1 Teacher's beliefs about the learning benefits of multimedia with visuals in teaching SW

According to the results of the interview, incorporating visual aids with multimedia in the classroom provides a number of benefits. When asked about the educators' views on the usage of visual aids with multimedia, all teachers agreed that they might be used in a variety of ways to enhance the learning experience of SW subjects. Teachers may make their SW classes more engaging by adding visual aids. The use of different images in the classroom helps to keep the attention of the pupils focused on the content of the lesson. From the findings of the interview, if the SW instructors in the classroom utilize various images that are linked to the lesson, the classes become more vibrant and the students, get over and above concept of the subject matter. It is usually preferable to have something visually appealing in front of the pupils in order for them to fully comprehend the lesson. Harmer (2001) is also mentioned that the use of photographs in the classroom makes the teaching more attractive.

The study reveals that PowerPoint presentations are a highly valuable visual aid for SW educators. From the teacher's interview, it is found that PowerPoint is the most popular visual tool for presenting any topic clearly. Teachers have a variety of options when it comes to using this powerful tool in their classrooms. When showing the necessary photographs, videos, or animations with the PPT, it makes the lecture easier to understand. Ozaslan and Maden (2013) also discovered similar findings in their research. Therefore, it has appeared recently as one of the most important tools for instructors.

Most of the instructors thought that videos were the most effective visual aids for assisting pupils in better understanding the subject matter. Students are comfortable when they are seeing videos that are linked to the subject matter. Their attention to the lecture becomes stronger, and they strive to connect the meaning of the words to the primary idea of the videos as much as they can. They also noted that there are several instructional videos available on YouTube that may be used to assist pupils in understanding or grasping certain subjects. Students like it when they are shown many videos about the same thing through PowerPoint and can understand the subject matter well because they are interested in it, which is supported by the findings of Erwin and Rieppi's (1999) study.

4.2.2 Dominant SW courses in which teachers use multimedia with visuals in their classes

According to the findings of the interview, there were a number of dominant SW courses where visual aids were utilized most frequently. Most of the teachers said that they use visual aids to teach many of the main courses in SW, such as Statistics, Demography, Human Growth and Development, Human Behavior and Psychology, Social Case Work and Group Work, Computer and so on. As an example, when they conduct Human behavior and Psychology class on the themes of human body structure or various phases of human growth, they often display photos and videos to their students in order to help them better comprehend the class content.

Ballantyne and Knowles (2007) stated that since it became possible to do so, creative SW teachers have used photos, music, and videos in their lessons to make them more interesting and fun. Therefore, the application of multimedia with visual contents are needed for interpretation of various aspects of Social Work subjects. Seabury and Maple (1993) placed a strong focus on the use of self-learning interactive videodisc technology to train Social Work students in the areas of Group Work, interviews, and crisis intervention, among other things. Overall, it was discovered that the majority of participants were optimistic about the program's success, believed they had obtained a better understanding of crisis theory, and believed they were better prepared to put the theory into practice.

4.2.3 Challenges of SW teachers who use multimedia for teaching visuals in their classes

All of the teachers said that they sometimes have trouble putting visual aids into their classes. A lack of multimedia classrooms and other digital equipment is one of the main problems here. There are not many teachers in the department; there is a deficit in an uninterrupted supply of electricity; and the internet connection is not very good. Only one multimedia classroom exists in the SW Department. Therefore, there is a crucial need for more classrooms to conduct frequent multimedia classes. There are certain difficulties in obtaining the required resources from the institution or the government. The Social Work department is suffering from financial challenges and does not get appropriate financing from the college. Babiker and Elmagzoub (2015) research also identified similar problems that face teachers when they use multimedia effectively in the classroom.

On the other hand, many instructors have to deal with the difficulty of creating visual presentations or PowerPoint slides for their students. In order to create effective PowerPoint slides or visual presentations, a significant amount of work and expertise is required. It takes a lot of time and effort for the SW instructors to generate quality content, yet they are seldom rewarded for their efforts. Consequently, this causes them to lose interest in developing visual multimedia classes frequently. Making visual content, they believe, is a tremendously time-consuming and labor-intensive activity. The problems that SW educators face in creating multimedia visual content are similar to the findings of the Sultana and Shahabul (2018) studies.

Conclusions

Educators throughout the world are eager to utilize multimedia technology in the classroom in order to make teachings more interesting for students (Tan, Kwok, Neo & Neo, 2010). Based on the discussions, it can be concluded that the usage of multimedia may enhance teaching and learning in order to make Social Work lessons more comprehensive and relevant to the student's knowledge (Ballantyne, 2008). The results show that multimedia may be useful for teaching through visuals in Social Work, and although the traditional technique is not appropriate in certain instances, but visual multimedia teaching approaches are effective in any context. The present study attempted to identify the utilization of multimedia with visuals for teaching Social Work in government colleges. The results of this study show that visual multimedia can make classes more interesting and easier to understand. Students may be able to help in a multimedia classroom because it can be motivating for them to learn. In addition, they were excited about the idea of multimedia classes that could help students and teachers spend more time together. Therefore, educators that get into visual multimedia in their classrooms are now reaping the benefits of this.

Recommendations

Some suggestions are made in light of the study's results. The teaching of Social Work using visual multimedia in Bangladeshi government colleges has been hampered by a lack of adequate infrastructure in educational institutions. Therefore, more resources would help with the low use of multimedia in the classroom, as suggested by Sultana and Hoque (2018). Expanding the number of multimedia classrooms is necessary to ensure that each academic year's worth of Social Work courses may be taught by using multimedia with visuals. In addition, a steady supply of power is more important for conducting the multimedia classes. Teachers should

be given the training they need to make better multimedia content for their lessons so that they can do well (Aloraini, 2012). The college authorities' ongoing support and technical training are essential for educators and learners to be able to integrate them into visual multimedia classrooms, with new technical pedagogical competencies and resources available. It is necessary to take the appropriate actions in order to alleviate the excessive workload on the educators in the department. When teachers learn how to make and use digital content and multimedia, they will be better able to teach their students. Therefore, educators need to get extra training in order to be better at teaching multimedia lessons. Finally, educators should be rewarded for their extra work in this area, and they should be given more time off.

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